

A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG POST GRADUATE STUDENTS IN MADURAI DISTRICT

Subashini J.T

Social Worker, Dementia Clinic, Government Rajaji Hospital, Tamil Nadu

Author Email: brindha.1159@gmail.com

Abstract— The study aims to measure the difference in the level of emotional intelligence with socio demographic details of age, gender, educational stream and marital status. Sixty participants were taken from the population of post graduate students from Madurai district by using the sampling technique of simple random sampling. Data collection was done by using the standardized questionnaire of Emotional Quotient Test (EQT) with the interviewing questions of socio demographic details. Hence, the study reported there is no significant difference was found in the socio demographic details such as age, gender, educational stream and marital status based on the level of emotional intelligence.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, age, gender, marital status, educational stream

I. INTRODUCTION

With the right communication and problem-solving techniques, emotional intelligence creates the perfect standard for children to know about themselves and to grow ethically. Emotional intelligence is the ability to regulate and control one's own emotions as well as the capacity to manage the emotion of others. Students with high emotional intelligence are good at controlling their stress and emotions, which allows them to handle difficulties more quickly and effectively. They can adjust to people with a range of temperaments and personalities. Most importantly, they have the ability to control their emotions to make wise choices whenever necessary. In this study, the researcher finds to measure the emotional intelligence of post graduate students in Madurai district.

A study explained that emotional intelligence is associated with positive mental health and emotionally intelligent people are a pleasant company whereas those lacking in emotional intelligence are generally maladjusted to their environment (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). The study suggested that principles like open-mindedness, inclusion, respect, and tolerance can be developed by promoting the development of Emotional Intelligence in students, based on Goleman's theory that emotional intelligence can be taught, arguments and research trying to support need for both emotional and intellectual development of the student through education (Sherlock, 2002). Although, a measure of emotional understanding was found to be related with academic success but this relationship lost ground when relevant cognitive abilities and personality characteristics were considered (Barchard, 2003).

In Addition, to identify the relationship of emotional intelligence with Big Five Personality dimensions, life satisfaction, feelings of powerlessness and job performance. The study concluded that, though Emotional Intelligence was related with Big Five Personality dimensions but was distinct from them. Emotional Intelligence was found to be positively associated with life satisfaction and job performance but negatively associated with feelings of powerlessness. (Law, Wong & Song, 2004). According to Daniel Goleman asserts that no gender differences in emotional intelligence exist, admitting that while men and women may have different profiles of strengths and weaknesses in different areas of emotional intelligence, their overall levels of emotional intelligence are equivalent (Daniel Goleman, 1998).

Moreover, the role of gender differences and age in emotional intelligence of undergraduate students studying in a large South-eastern university. They found that females had higher levels of emotional intelligence than males and age had a positive and significant association with emotional intelligence. (Van Rooy, Alonso and Viswesvaran, 2005). Furthermore, research on the age group of 22 to 70 years with emotional intelligence has found that age has a positive and significant association with Emotional intelligence also they asserted that the older people have slightly higher emotional intelligence. (Fariselli, Ghini & Freedman, 2006)

II. METHODOLOGY

II.I. AIM

To study the emotional intelligence of the postgraduate students by comparing with their age group, gender, educational stream and marital status in Madurai district

II.II. OBJECTIVES

1. To study the socio demographic profile of the respondents
2. To assess the emotional intelligence of the respondents

Hypothesis

There is a significant age difference based on the level of emotional intelligence

There is a significant gender difference based on the level of emotional intelligence

There is a significant educational stream difference based on the level of emotional intelligence

There is a significant marital status difference based on the level of emotional intelligence

II.III. SAMPLE

Sample was collected from the Postgraduate students who are studying master degree in Madurai District. The sample size of this study were 60 students (N = 60) with 30 male and 30 female post graduate students. The inclusion criteria of this study were post graduate students from Madurai district and the students who doesn't belong to the district of Madurai and/or having any physical or mental health issues can be excluded from this study. Simple random sampling method was adopted for the study.

II.IV. VARIABLES

The present study concentrates the emotional intelligence and socio-economic variable was used for the study.

Tools Used

- Socio Demographic Details
- Emotional Quotient Test (EQT)

Description of the Tools

Socio Demographic Details

The socio demographic factors such as age, gender, occupation, marital status, and educational stream.

Emotional Quotient Test (EQT)

Emotional quotient test was developed by Dr Dalip Singh & Dr NK Chadha (2003). It is used to measure the emotional intelligence of individuals. It is a self-report measure inventory which consists of 22 items. The retest reliability for the test was found to be 0.94.

II.V. PROCEDURE

The researcher explained the purpose of the research to the respondents and conduct interview with each respondent using the interview schedule meant for assessing socio demographic factors, The Emotional Intelligence Scale. The interview was conducted in a class room atmosphere with a proper consent form.

II.VI. DATA ANALYSIS

The data analysis will be done by using the statistical methods of descriptive and inferential statistics such as mean, standard deviation, independent t test and One way ANOVA with the help of statistical package of SPSS 16.0.

III. RESULTS

Table 1

Shows the frequency and percentage of age group of the respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-21	19	31.7
22-24	37	61.7
25-26	4	6.6
Total	60	100.0

This table shows 31.7% of the respondents' age coming under the 18-20, 61.7% of the respondents coming under the age of 21-23, 6.7% of the respondents coming under the age of 24-26.

Table 2

Shows the frequency and percentage of Gender of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	30	50.0
Female	30	50.0
Total	60	100.0

This table shows 50% of the respondents are male, 50% of the respondents are female.

Table 3

Shows the frequency and percentage of Educational Stream of the Respondents

Educational stream	Frequency	Percentage
Arts	18	30.0
Science	20	33.3
Business	22	36.7
Total	60	100.0

From the above table, 36.7% of the respondents are from Business stream, 33% of the respondents are from science stream and 30% of the respondents are from arts stream.

Table 4

Shows the frequency and percentage of marital status of the respondents

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	6	10.0
Unmarried	54	90.0
Total	60	100.0

From the above table, 90% of the respondents are Unmarried and 10% of the respondents were married.

Table 5

Shows the frequency and percentage of type of family of the respondents

Type of Family	Frequency	Percentage
Nuclear	39	65.0
Joint	21	35.0
Total	60	100.0

From the above table, 65% of the respondents are in nuclear type of family and 35% of the respondents are in Joint family.

Table 6

Shows the frequency and percentage of Level of Emotional Intelligence

Level of Emotional Intelligence	Frequency	Percentage
Low level	15	25%
Moderate level	28	46.7%
High level	17	28.3%
Total	60	100.0

From the above table, 46% of the students are in moderate level, 28% of the students are in high level and 25% of the students are in Low level. This shows that the greater number of students are in moderate level.

Table 7

Shows the independent t- test to measure the gender difference

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-test scores	Df	Sig. Value

Emotional Intelligence	Male	30	1.80	.664	-2.571	58	.291
	Female	30	2.27	.740			

This table shows that ($p < .05$) its P value is .291 level of significance, the null hypothesis accepted, the alternative hypothesis rejected. Hence there is significance relationship between level of emotional intelligence and gender.

Table 8

Shows the independent t- test to measure the marital status difference

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-test scores	Df	Sig. Value
Emotional Intelligence	Married	6	2.17	.753	.465	58	.961
	Unmarried	54	2.02	.739			

This table shows that ($p < .05$) its P value is .961 level of significance, the null hypothesis accepted, the alternative hypothesis rejected. Hence there is significance relationship between level of Emotional intelligence and marital status.

Table 9

Shows the ANOVA to measure the educational stream difference

Variable	Educational stream	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F value	Df	Sig. Value
Emotional Intelligence	Science	20	2.15	.671	.565	59	.572
	Arts	18	2.06	.802			
	Business	22	1.91	.750			

This table shows that ($p < .05$) its p value is .527 so the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected hence the significance difference between level of EI and educational stream

Table 10

Shows the ANOVA to measure the age group difference

Variable	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F value	Df	Sig. Value
Emotional Intelligence	18-20	19	1.89	.737	.524	59	.595
	21-23	37	2.11	.737			
	24-26	4	2.00	.816			

This table shows that ($p < .05$) its p value is .595 so the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected hence the significance difference between level of EI and Age.

IV. DISCUSSION

The above test results reported, 61.7% of the respondents coming under the age of 21-23, 50% of the respondents are male, 50% of the respondents are female. 36.7% of the respondents are from Business stream, 90% of the respondents are Unmarried and 10% of the respondents were married, 65% of the respondents are in nuclear type of family, 46% of the students are in moderate level, 28% of the students are in high level and 25% of the students are in Low level. This shows that the greater number of students are in moderate level. According to t-test analysis, the findings reported about the difference in gender categories of male and female has a P value of 0.291 level of significance which is more than 0.05. This indicates, the null hypothesis accepted and the alternative hypothesis rejected. Hence there is no significance relationship between the categories of gender based on the level of emotional intelligence. Also, the marital status difference categories of married and unmarried has a P value of 0.961 level of significance which is more than 0.05 that is, the null hypothesis accepted and the alternative hypothesis rejected. Hence there is no significance relationship between the categories of marital status based on the level of emotional intelligence. According to the analysis of One-way ANOVA, the findings reported about the difference in educational stream categories of arts, science and business has a P value of 0.527 which is more than 0.05 that is so the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected hence there is no significance difference between the categories of educational stream based on the level of emotional intelligence. Also, the age group categories of 18-20 years old, 21-23 years old and 24-26 years old has a P value 0.592 which is more than 0.05 that is so the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected hence the significance difference between the age group categories based on the level of emotional intelligence.

V. CONCLUSION

This study sought to address the question of Emotional Intelligence of the Post Graduate. It is apparent that students develop Emotional Intelligence skills during their college studies. This research aligned with previous literature which suggested that EI skill growth is important to student success and personally. According to the 60 students who participated in the study 25% of the respondents have high emotional intelligence 46.7% of the respondents have moderate level of Emotional Intelligence and 28.3% of the respondents are low emotional intelligence. Reframing of Education systems with Emotional Intelligence components will improve the life style of the students

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